

TEAPOTS

Agriculture waste pyrolysis and thermo composting for
renewable energy in sustainable agri-food sector

GOAL

TEAPOTS aims to give agri-food players an innovative integrated, modular, and flexible solution to meet local and seasonal energy demand through the valorisation of lignocellulosic and difficult to be treated agricultural waste while producing biochar. **TEAPOTS** will leverage onto two clusters:

Teapots Integrated Solution - TIS integrates four technologies (Pyrolysis, Compost Heat Recovery System, Organic Rankine Cycle, Dry Cooler & Oil-free AWC) that will be able to satisfy agricultural waste management & energy needs and promote own energy consumption of renewable and cost-efficient carbon-neutral decentralized production of renewable energy. **TIS** will enable a circular approach to support biomass treatment and valorisation at a local level to optimise farm production.

Teapots Digital Platform - TDP integrates different ICT systems in a common platform (Integrated Database of satellite Data, Field Sensors, and TIS data; Prediction system of biomass yields & logistics; Data-driven Decision Support System) allowing fine control of biomass production thanks to a model-based prediction of middle-term production and future biomass availability. **TDP** will foster regional development in rural areas and support farmers' engagement as renewable energy prosumers.

DEMONSTRATIONS

The **TEAPOTS** project showcases its innovative solutions through two physical pilot sites in Italy and Greece, testing processes and refining results.

To broaden its impact, virtual replication studies are conducted in Germany and the Netherlands, assessing adaptability to diverse environments and feedstocks.

Different dimensions of end-users, such as those in France, are also evaluated, ensuring scalability and relevance across regions.

FUNDING

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101118296. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

OBJECTIVES

Agri-waste management to meet end-users' seasonal energy demand

Technology development to meet farmers' economics

Soil and biodiversity improvement

Decreasing the environmental impact of agriculture through waste management

Farmers' empowerment as prosumers to increase societal impact

TEAPOTS

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